

*An Exact Confidence Interval for Difference of Two Proportions
with Stratified factors*

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In clinical trials, a confidence interval (CI) of difference of two proportions with stratified factors is often calculated by the Miettinen, O. and Nurminen, M (M&N) method[1]. For rare events where incidence rate is low, the normality assumption of the method for analyzing the between treatment difference could be problematic. In this presentation, we propose an exact method to obtain a CI for difference of two proportions with stratified factors, dropping the assumption of normality. The propose method is developed using following steps: First, we expand the idea in Exact (Clopper-Pearson) Confidence Limits to handle the stratification factors. Next, with this new exact formula of CI, we define a posterior distribution on each observed proportion with stratification factors. Finally, we create a CI based on these two posterior distributions. The proposed method does not require normality assumption or a Beta prior to define a posterior on observed proportions for statistical inference.

1. Define posterior distribution by formula of Exact (Clopper-Pearson) Confidence Limits without stratification

For binary data with probability of success p , let us consider we want to use the observed proportion \hat{p} to get an estimated posterior distribution of p . With posterior distributions from both active p_a and placebo p_p group, we can obtain the estimated distribution of differences ($p_a - p_p$) of two proportions and construct a confidence interval without making a normality assumption.

To get around the need of selecting a pair (α, β) for the Beta prior, used in the Bayesian method to derive a posterior on an observe proportion $\hat{p} = n_1/n$, we propose using the method of exact Clopper-Pearson confidence limits to define a posterior distribution directly on the observe proportion \hat{p} .

The method, attributed to Clopper and Pearson (1934) to get exact confidence confident limits is explained as follows:

Exact (Clopper-Pearson) Confidence Limits confidence limits for the binomial proportion are constructed by inverting the equal-tailed test based on the binomial distribution.. The exact confidence limits pL and pU satisfy the following equations, for $m = 1, 2, \dots, n - 1$:

$$\sum_{x=m}^n \text{Bin}(x, pL, n) = \alpha/2$$

$$\sum_{x=0}^m \text{Bin}(x, pU, n) = \alpha/2$$

where

$$pL = \left(1 + \frac{n - m + 1}{m F(\alpha/2, 2(m_1 + 1), 2(n - m + 1))}\right)^{-1}$$

$$pU = \left(1 + \frac{n - m + 1}{m + 1} F(1 - \alpha/2, 2m, 2(n - m))\right)^{-1}$$

The lower confidence limit equals 0 when event $m = 0$, and the upper confidence limit equals 1 when event $m = n$, where $F(\alpha/2, b, c)$ is the $\alpha/2$ percentile of the F distribution with b and c degrees of freedom.

If $\alpha/2 = 0.025$ with fixed m and n , $pL(0.025)$ is a proportion p that has 2.5% probability to observe m or more events.

There is a natural way to define a cumulative distribution function (CDF) from any formula of confidence limit, based on the observed data. Using pU as an example, with fixed n_1 and n , it is a function of $(1 - \alpha/2)$ and the corresponding CDF can be defined as $\{pU(X), X\}$ for X in $(0,1)$ as a posterior distribution.

$$pU = \left(1 + \frac{n - n_1 + 1}{(n_1 + 1) F(1 - \alpha/2, 2n_1, 2(n - n_1))}\right)^{-1}$$

Method Details

We choose 100 probability points to illustrate the steps of how to define a discrete posterior distribution, but for any number of points, the procedure is the same.

Steps to define a discrete posterior distribution on the observed $\hat{p} = n_1/n$

1. Define a 100 point sequence of $\{a\} = \{0.005, 0.015, \dots, 0.995\}$.
2. Plug each CDF value of $\{a\}$ into the formula for pL to replace $\alpha/2$ to get the sequence $pL(\{a\})$.
3. This defines a discrete posterior distribution on $\hat{p} = n_1/n$. One percent probability is automatically assigned to each value in the sequence of $pL(\{a\})$.

4. Plug each value in $\{a\}$ into the formula for pU to replace $(1- \alpha/2)$ to get the sequence $pU(\{a\})$.

5. This defines another discrete posterior distribution on $\hat{p} = n_1/n$. One percent probability is again automatically assigned to each value in the sequence of $pU(\{a\})$.

6. if $n_1 = 0$ then $p = pU(\{a\})$

7. if $n_1 = n$ then $p = pL(\{a\})$

8. If $n_1 > 0$ and $n_1 < n$, we define the discrete posterior distribution of 100 points on $\hat{p} = n_1/n$ as

$$p = \{pL(\{a\}), pU(\{a\})\}$$

with

50 points from $pL(\{a\})$ for $\{a\}$ in $\{0.005, 0.015, \dots, 0.495\}$ and

50 points from $pU(\{a\})$ for $\{a\}$ in $\{0.505, 0.015, \dots, 0.995\}$.

All above posterior distributions would have the same confidence limits as defined by *Clopper and Pearson* formula.

2. Extending *Clopper-Pearson* Formula with information of stratification factors

Following example provides illustration of the proposed method:

2.1 Assuming observed $p = m/n = 20/50 = 0.4$ and 2 strata are $m = m_1 + m_2 = 5 + 15$ and $n = n_1 + n_2 = 25 + 25$.

2.2 Without stratification, the exact 95% CI of $p = 20/50$ is (0.264, 0.548) by *Clopper-Pearson* formula. That is, the upper bound satisfies

$$\sum_{x=0}^{20} Bin(x, 0.548, 50) = 0.025$$

2.3 With additional information on stratification factors, the 95% CI should be narrower or at least not wider. Therefore, in this example, the upper bound should be less than or equal to 0.548.

2.4. Let us assume that the new upper bound limit of 95% CI was $0.547 < 0.548$, but

$$\sum_{x=0}^{20} \text{Bin}(x, 0.547, 50) = 0.026 > 0.025$$

2.5. So we have to make adjustment to get probability 0.025 yielding a lowered upper bound when strata information is incorporated.

2.6. Constructing the confidence interval with strata information provides a natural from observed strata data and can be extended from 2 to many strata.

Proposed Method (continue to use above numerical example)

For $pU=0.548$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} 0.025 &= \sum_{x=0}^{20} \text{Bin}(x, pU, 50) \\ &= \sum_{x=0}^{19} \text{Bin}(x, pU, 50) + \text{Bin}(20, pU, 50) \\ &= \sum_{x=0}^{19} \text{Bin}(x, pU, 50) + \\ &\quad \sum_{y=0}^{20} \text{Bin}(y, pU, 25) * \text{Bin}(20 - y, pU, 25) \\ &= A + \sum_{y=0}^{20} C(y) \quad \text{where} \\ A &= \sum_{x=0}^{19} \text{Bin}(x, pU, 50) \text{ and} \\ C(y) &= \text{Bin}(y, pU, 25) * \text{Bin}(20 - y, pU, 25), y=0, 1, \dots, 20. \end{aligned}$$

With $m_1=5$, $m_2=15$ and $n_1=n_2=25$,

let $B = Bin(m_1, pU, n_1) * Bin(m_2, pU, n_2)$, we will remove the events $C(y)$ that is larger than B .

Now we search for pU , that satisfies

$$pU: A + \text{Sum}[C(y), \text{ for } C(y) \leq B, \text{ where } y = 0, 1, \dots, 20] = 0.025 \quad \dots(\mathbf{A})$$

This pU is our new upper bound of 95% CI with added stratum information.

Note both A and $C(y)$ are function of pU . We have to use numerical method to search for pU .

Definition of proposed exact CI method with K strata

Assume observed proportion $p = m/n$ in K strata of m_i/n_i with

$$m = \sum_{i=1}^K m_i \text{ and } n = \sum_{i=1}^K n_i$$

Let

$$U = \sum_{x=0}^{m-1} Bin(x, p, n)$$

$$L = \sum_{x=m+1}^n Bin(x, p, n)$$

$$B = \prod_{i=1}^K Bin(m_i, p, n_i)$$

$$C(p, m, n) = \prod_{i=1}^K Bin(y_i, p, n_i)$$

$$\text{with } m = \sum_{i=1}^K y_i, \quad y_i \geq 0 \text{ and } n = \sum_{i=1}^K n_i$$

Find upper bound bound pU of 95% CI, that satisfies

$$U + \text{Sum}[C(pU, m, n)] = 0.025,$$

$$\text{for } C(pU, m, n) \leq B \text{ over all } m = \sum_{i=1}^K y_i, \quad y_i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, m$$

Find lower bound pL of 95% CI, that satisfies

$$L + \text{Sum}[C(pL, m, n)] = 0.025,$$

$$\text{for } C(pL, m, n) \leq B \text{ over all } m = \sum_{i=1}^K y_i, \quad y_i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, m$$

Similarly, we can define any other confidence limits of $1-\alpha$.

Numerical Examples

(1) Example of observed $p = 0.4$

Let $n=50, m=20, p=20/50=0.4$

$n_1=25, m_1=5, p_1=5/25=0.2$

Comparison of 95% CI			
Method	95% CI without strata	95% CI with strata	Ratio of Width
Normal method	(0.264, 0.536)	(0.276, 0.524)	91%
New Exact method	(0.264, 0.548)	(0.282, 0.529)	87%
Normal method: $0.4 \pm 1.96 \cdot \sqrt{\text{var}}$			

(2) Example of rare event: $m_1+m_2=m=4, p=0.08$

Let $n=50, m=4, p=4/50=0.08, n_1 = n_2 = 25$

exact 95% CI Clopper-Pearson		exact 95% CI with strata						ratio of width of CI
Lower	Upper	Lower	Upper	n1	m1	n2	m2	
0.022228	0.192340	0.022228	0.192340	25	2	25	2	100%
0.022228	0.192340	0.024928	0.18444	25	1	25	3	93.77%
0.022228	0.192340	0.031150	0.16978	25	0	25	4	81.49%

The examples demonstrate a relatively narrower width of confidence intervals when strata information is incorporated.

3. Method to find exact confidence interval for difference of two proportions with stratification factors

This method is similar as before when there is no stratification. We start with a 100 CDF point sequence of $\{a\}=\{0.005, 0.015, \dots, 0.995\}$ and try to find P value for each CDF(P) point. But this time we need to use recursive algorithm to find them with a pre-specified accuracy.

3.1 Bounds of Upper confidence limits with strata

The upper bound pU of upper confidence limit defined by

$$\sum_{x=0}^m Bin(x, pU, n) = \alpha/2$$

And

The lower bound pL of upper confidence limit defined by

$$\sum_{x=0}^{m-1} Bin(x, pL, n) = \alpha/2$$

Similar for Bounds of lower confidence limits pL with strata.

These limits define the initial interval for numerical iterations.

3.2 Examples

For a given \mathbf{c} , and observed $p=m/n$ and stratum $p_1 = m_1/n_1$, we need to find the P with CDF(P)=(1-c).

Initial upper and lower bound p_1 and p_2 of P can be found by

$$\sum_{x=0}^m Bin(x, p_1, n) = c \text{ and } \sum_{x=0}^{m-1} Bin(x, p_2, n) = c.$$

Then use formula (A) to find corresponding c_1 and c_2

Obtain the updated \mathbf{p} by solving $(p_1-p_2)/(c_1-c_2) = (p-p_2)/(c-c_2)$

and use formula (A) to find updated c. Until it equals to target \mathbf{c} .

Examples : Let $n=50$, $m=20$, $p=20/50=0.4$ $n_1=25$, $m_1=5$ $p_1=5/25$

Find P in $CDF(P)=1-c$ with $c=0.025$ and 0.625 :

iteration	p_1	c_1	p_2	c_2	updated		target
					p	c	c
Initial	.54821	.01259	.52825	.02519			.025
1	.54821	.01259	.52825	.02519	.52855	.02494	.025
2	.52855	.02494	.52825	.02519			.025
2	.52855	.02494	.52825	.02519	.52848	.025001	.025
3	.52855	.02494	.52848	.02500			.025
3	.52855	.02494	.52848	.02500	.52848	.025000	.025
Find $CDF(0.52848)=0.975$ with $abs(c- target\ c) < 10^{**}(-6)$							
Initial	.38868	.51294	.36902	.62589			.625
1	.38868	.51294	.36902	.62589	.36917	.62502	.625
2	.36917	.62502	.36902	.62589			.625
2	.36917	.62502	.36902	.62589	.36918	.62500	.625
Find $CDF(0.36918)=0.375$							

In most cases, it takes 3 or less iterations to convergence.

With above data, it takes less than 1 second to get a 1,000 points CDF for $\{1- c\} = \{0.0005, 0.0015, \dots, 0.9995\}$.

Comparison of proposed Exact method with M&N method for difference of two observed proportions with/without strata

Consider data set with 2 strata a and b: each defined by a 2x2 table

$na=50, ma=20, na_1=25, pa=0.4, pa_1=ma_1/na_1 = ma_1/25$
 $nb=50, mb=20, nb_1=25, pb=0.4, pb_1=mb_1/nb_1 = mb_1/25$

	95CI% width Without strata	95%CI width With strata	ma1	mb1
M&N	0.18988	0.19081	10	10
Exact	0.20676	0.20676	10	10
M&N	0.18988	0.16135	5	5
Exact	0.20676	0.17048	5	5
M&N	0.18988	0.12175	2	2
Exact	0.20676	0.17011	2	2
M&N	0.18988	0.10128	1	1
Exact	0.20676	0.17011	1	1
M&N	0.18988	0.07269	0	0
Exact	0.20676	0.17011	0	0

Conclusions

- The proposed method extended the exact Clopper-Pearson confidence limits methods to incorporate information of stratification factors.
- The confidence intervals around observed proportions are narrower, as expected, by including stratification factors.
- Using the proposed exact method, we can define a confidence interval of the difference of two proportions without normality assumption.

References:

- [1] Miettinen, O. and Nurminen, M. (1985), “Comparative Analysis of Two Rates,” *Statistics in Medicine*, 4, 213–226.
- [2] Clopper, C. J. and Pearson, E. S. (1934), “The Use of Confidence or Fiducial Limits Illustrated in the Case of the Binomial,” *Biometrika*, 26, 404–413.
- [3] Yao R, Kaur A, Li Q “An Alternative Method to Find the Confidence Interval for the Difference Between Two Proportions of Rare Event” Biometrics Section—JSM 2021 Proceedings.
- [4] Yao R, Kaur A, Li Q “An Exact Confidence Interval of Observed Proportion with Stratified factors” Biometrics Section—JSM 2022 Proceedings.